

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF GLUCOCORTICOID PRICES IN THE TREATMENT OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

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Relevance: rheumatoid arthritis is a chronic autoimmune disease of connective tissue, characterized by progressive joint damage and deformity, as well as the development of disability. Contemporary pharmacotherapy includes disease-modifying ant rheumatic drugs, biological agents, and symptomatic treatment. Glucocorticoids are administered in combination with other therapeutic agents and play an important role in controlling the inflammatory process and managing disease exacerbations. International and national clinical guidelines confirm their efficacy and widespread application, which highlights the relevance of analyzing the availability of these medications.

Purpose of the study: is to conduct a comparative analysis of the prices of prednisolone and methylprednisolone recommended in the national clinical protocol for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis.

Materials and methods: the study utilized data from the "Farm Portal" ("Reference Price List") as of September 14, 2025. A comparative analysis was performed on the retail prices of prednisolone and methylprednisolone pharmaceutical products, categorized by international non-proprietary names and brand names, with consideration of dosage forms and manufacturers.

Results: the analysis revealed that the range of prednisolone and methylprednisolone medications is represented by multiple brand names produced by different manufacturers.

№	International non-proprietary name	Brand names	Manufacturer	Retail price, UZS	Country of origin
1	Prednisolone	Prednisolone -RG 30 mg/ml, 1 ml, № 5 (1x5)	Remedy Group JV Ltd.	23,184	Uzbekistan
2		Prednisolone 30 mg/ml 1 ml, № 10	Radiks Ltd.	34,003.2	Uzbekistan
3		Prednisolone -RG 30 mg/ml, 1 ml, №10 (2x5)	Remedy Group JV Ltd.	30,912	Uzbekistan
4		Prednisolone 30 mg/ml 1 ml, № 10 (2x5)	Ellara Ltd.	29,951.14	Russia
5		Prednisolone 30 mg/ml 1 ml, № 5 (1x5)	Uzgermed Pharm JV Ltd.	33,120	Uzbekistan
6		Prednisolone SD 5 mg, № 50 (5x10)	Sharq Darmon Ltd.	29,566.5	Uzbekistan

7		Prednisolone 5 mg, № 40 (2x20)	JSC Vinh phuc pharmaceutical	41,659.6 1	Vietnam
8		Prednisolone-Darnytsia 5 mg, № 40 (4x10)	PrJSC Darnytsia	34,211.5 7	Ukraine
9		Prednisolone 5 mg, № 100 (10x10)	Co.ltd. Shandong Xier Kangtai Pharmaceutical	35,671.4 8	China
10		Prednisolone 30 mg/ml 1 ml, № 3 (3x1)	Agio Pharmaceuticals Ltd.	18,006.1	India
11		Prednisolone 5 mg, № 100 (10x10)	Aburaihan Pharmaceutical Co.	54,282.0 3	Iran
12	Methylprednisolone	Solu-Medrol 500 mg	Pfizer Manufacturing Belgium NV	272,189. 92	Belgium
13		Solu-Medrol 1000 mg	Pfizer Manufacturing Belgium NV	571,385. 76	Belgium
14		Avimedrol 4 mg, № 30 (3x10)	Avantika Medex Pvt. Ltd.	112,690. 57	India
15		Avimedrol 16 mg, № 30 (3x10)	Avantika Medex Pvt. Ltd.	270,457. 37	India
16		Slideron 4 mg, № 20 (2x10)	AD Balkanpharma-Razgrad	89,931.0 4	Bulgaria
17		Slideron 16 mg, № 20 (2x10)	AD Balkanpharma-Razgrad	213,975. 24	Bulgaria
18		Slideron 500 mg	LTD United Biotech (P)	134,363. 7	India

The range of prednisolone medications is represented by different formulations: ampoules (30 mg/ml) priced from 18,006.1 to 34,003.2 UZS, and tablets (5 mg) priced from 29,566.5 to 54,282.03 UZS. The range of methylprednisolone medications includes intravenous formulations (500-1000 mg) priced from 134,363.7 to 571,385.76 UZS, and tablets (4-16 mg) priced from 89,931.04 to 270,457.37 UZS. These findings indicate that methylprednisolone constitutes a significantly more expensive therapeutic option compared to prednisolone, with the greatest cost difference observed for injections.

Conclusions: the comparative analysis demonstrated that methylprednisolone pharmaceutical products are, on average, 3-10 times more expensive than prednisolone, which may substantially reduce their accessibility for patients. Furthermore, the price variation within each drug group reaches

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up to twofold, indicating considerable market heterogeneity. These findings underscore the necessity of incorporating price considerations into strategies for ensuring equitable access to essential medicines. They also emphasize the importance of rational drug selection within clinical protocols and the potential need for policy measures aimed at improving affordability and optimizing resource allocation in healthcare systems.